

Additional file 6: Detailed results related to Figure 2 – Results of logistic regression model (odds ratios and standard errors)

	<i>Specialist use</i>	<i>GP use</i>	<i>Specialist unmet needs</i>	<i>GP unmet needs</i>	<i>Emergency dept. use</i>	<i>Avoidable hospitalization</i>
<i>HV (ref. regular access)</i>	0.405*** (0.0972)	0.614 (0.192)	0.937 (0.243)	0.953 (0.258)	0.736 (0.158)	0.952 (0.291)
<i>EHC (ref. regular access)</i>	0.967 (0.360)	1.336 (0.593)	1.887* (0.612)	0.870 (0.314)	0.991 (0.321)	1.689 (0.558)
<i>Age</i>	1.001 (0.00916)	0.999 (0.00992)	1.004 (0.0101)	0.990 (0.0109)	0.976** (0.0117)	0.991 (0.0116)
<i>Male (ref. female)</i>	1.386* (0.255)	1.619** (0.344)	1.054 (0.205)	1.039 (0.228)	2.238*** (0.413)	1.035 (0.262)
<i>Time since arrival (months)</i>	0.997 (0.00351)	1.004 (0.00401)	0.999 (0.00307)	1.006 (0.00367)	0.995 (0.00332)	0.998 (0.00356)
<i>Region: Asia (ref. Europe)</i>	1.000 (0.307)	1.880** (0.540)	1.246 (0.441)	0.928 (0.286)	0.750 (0.184)	1.026 (0.290)
<i>Region: Africa (ref. Europe)</i>	1.358 (0.515)	1.571 (0.538)	1.232 (0.550)	0.949 (0.334)	0.910 (0.332)	1.563 (0.631)
<i>Region: Other (ref. Europe)</i>	1.330 (0.618)	1.991* (0.765)	1.180 (0.475)	1.015 (0.444)	1.229 (0.520)	1.312 (0.655)

<i>Rather bad general health (ref. rather good)</i>	2.430*** (0.478)	1.854** (0.504)	2.323*** (0.437)	2.363*** (0.576)	1.499* (0.345)	1.752** (0.454)
<i>No chronic illness (ref. yes)</i>	1.099 (0.223)	2.516*** (0.681)	2.069*** (0.458)	2.482*** (0.600)	1.789** (0.436)	3.103*** (0.784)
<i>Education: low (ref. high)</i>	1.318 (0.332)	0.868 (0.201)	1.009 (0.246)	0.644* (0.152)	1.133 (0.320)	1.233 (0.325)
<i>Education: middle (ref. high)</i>	1.412 (0.317)	0.933 (0.243)	0.907 (0.195)	0.821 (0.195)	0.763 (0.203)	0.749 (0.206)
<i>No family doctor (ref. yes)</i>	1.931*** (0.451)	3.209*** (0.663)	0.643** (0.120)	0.922 (0.186)	1.886*** (0.414)	1.798*** (0.337)
<i>Reception centre (ref. accommodation centre)</i>	1.498 (0.415)	1.975** (0.606)	0.776 (0.336)	0.819 (0.305)	0.870 (0.244)	0.755 (0.269)
<i>Constant</i>	0.166*** (0.105)	0.100*** (0.0657)	0.300 (0.224)	0.436 (0.302)	0.766 (0.467)	0.179** (0.124)
<i>Observations</i>	863	863	863	863	863	863
<i>p-value (F-test)</i>	0.479	0.779	0.420	0.681	0.849	>0.001

Standard errors in parentheses; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$